

Statement of Teaching Philosophy

Current events such as the anti-vaccination movement in the U.S demonstrate how misunderstandings of biocultural processes can have far-reaching social and political implications. Such examples highlight the need for effective instruction regarding the relationship between culture and biology in today's universities. As a bioarchaeologist who studies human skeletal remains I have a clear appreciation of the intricate relationship between biology and culture which has influenced my goals as an educator. One of my primary goals is to provide students with an understanding of how our evolutionary history has shaped key cultural and anatomical aspects of modern human existence. Another is to equip students to critically evaluate the information and interpretations that they are regularly exposed to through popular media, providing them with a foundation for becoming informed members of the public regardless of their future career aspirations.

I use three pedagogical strategies to enact these goals. First, I teach key concepts in anthropology in ways that encourage students to relate them to their own lives, making difficult or unfamiliar concepts more tangible. For example, in *Archaeology of Inequality*, I open a class unit on decision-making and scalar stress by asking progressively larger groups of students to select the best place to hide during a zombie attack. This activity encourages students to consider the informational benefits and organizational drawbacks of dealing with greater numbers of people and larger volumes of information—problems that have been argued to precipitate the emergence of hierarchical forms of organization in past societies. In my introductory course *Written in Bone*, I ask students to collect data from cars parked on campus and compares the state listed on the license plate to the geographic information encoded in bumper stickers. Their results are used to open a discussion about how distinct types of archaeological evidence—for example, strontium isotope ratios and mortuary treatment—can produce dissonant interpretations of mobility and regional affiliation in past populations. In the future, I will continue to employ active learning techniques when teaching courses such as *Introduction to Archaeology* and *European Prehistory*, using contemporary fashion trends to discuss the interpretation of artifact styles and touring campus landmarks to explore issues of visibility and accessibility in prehistoric monuments.

The second strategy I employ to achieve my teaching goals is to provide an interdisciplinary approach that requires students to consider how evidence is presented in academic publications and in the media. I use historic and contemporary personal ads to demonstrate patterning in mate choice and select popular case studies like the Paleodiet or GMOs that allow students to critically evaluate contemporary phenomena in relation to their growing understanding of human evolution. These strategies encourage students to actively assess how scientific material is portrayed in the popular media and teach them how to marshal scientific evidence in order to clearly argue their perspective to diverse groups of peers. In my first-year writing seminars, students read excerpts of complex anthropology articles and then worked in small groups to evaluate the hypotheses and methodology that at first seemed concealed by scientific jargon. By breaking topics down into short, manageable assignments and encouraging small and large group discussion, I

teach students how to assess scientific evidence that that has been communicated in a variety of ways.

Finally, I structure an interactive learning environment that ensures that all students participate in my courses. I teach topics such as reciprocal altruism and the prisoner's dilemma with interactive simulations, using M&Ms to represent common pool resources. In my skeletal anatomy classes, I assign quiz questions that require students to craft clay models of bones to internalize their knowledge of osteology, and drive students to construct hypotheses about locomotion by measuring the bones of chimpanzees and australopithecines. I also vary the format and structure of discussion sections, using techniques like brainstorming sessions and "think-pair-share" to encourage students to discuss topics with a wide range of their peers. These strategies facilitate interaction between students of diverse cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds, ensuring that both shier and more extroverted students participate. I assess my teaching goals by evaluating levels of student engagement through attendance, participation tallying, and short in-class assignments. I also distribute mid-term evaluations in each of my classes and use student feedback to structure my pedagogical approach to the rest of the semester.

In sum, all of my pedagogical strategies are dedicated to highlighting the complex relationship between culture and biology in hands-on, engaging ways that will provide the critical thinking skills and scientific literacy necessary for students to be informed members of society, both inside and outside of the classroom. To date, my teaching has yielded two departmental teaching awards, and a Rackham Graduate School Outstanding Graduate Instructor Award, given to only 20 out of 2,000 instructors per year. I look forward to continuing to advance new strategies that will allow future generations of students to develop a critical and nuanced understanding of biocultural interactions, both in the past and in contemporary societies.